

The deterioration of spice crops caused by the contaminating fungi

¹Smita Rajput and ²Dr. Monica Agrawal

¹Research Scholar, Department of Microbiology, Swami Vivekanand University Sagar, Madhya Pradesh, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Excellent Bio Research Solutions Pvt. Ltd., Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14726133>

Corresponding Author: Smita Rajput

Abstract

Fungal contamination of various foodstuffs and agricultural commodities is a major problem in the tropics and subtropics, where climatic conditions and agricultural and storage practices are conducive to fungal growth and toxin production. Contamination of food and agricultural commodities by various types of toxigenic (fungi) is a serious and a widely neglected problem. Regardless of decades of extensive research, mould infection still remains a challenging problem (Munkvold, 2003).

Keywords: Spice, crops, fungi, mycotoxins, Microbiology

Introduction

Aflatoxins are produced by different fungal species that belong to the genus *Aspergillus* and more specifically to the Flavi section. For years, three main aflatoxigenic species were commonly considered in the section Flavi: *A. flavus*, *A. parasiticus* and *A. nomius*. In the last decade, the use of molecular tools enabled the identification of new species belonging to the section Flavi, comprising 34 different species, of which 17 are aflatoxigenic. These species can be distinguished by subtle morphological specificities, molecular changes in some gene sequences and, most importantly, through their ability to produce different mycotoxins. Indeed, some species, including *A. flavus*, *A. pseudotamarii* and *A. togoensis*, produce aflatoxins of B type, whereas others, including *A. parasiticus*, *A. minisclerotigenes*, *A. mottae*, *A. nomius*, *A. novoparasiticus*, *A. arachidicola* and *A. korhogoensis* produce both B and G type aflatoxins. Some species may also produce other toxic secondary metabolites such as cyclopiazonic acid (Kumar *et al.*, 2017) [2].

Most of the mycotoxins are easily absorbed from the site of exposure, such as the gastrointestinal (i.e., dietary consumption) or respiratory tract (i.e., inhalation dust), to the circulatory system reaching vital, as the toxin is distributed throughout the body. Mycotoxins can enter human and animal cells and exert a spectrum of effects, including permanent damage. Through natural cellular

processes of transcription and translation, these mutations may manifest or even exacerbate deregulation of cell growth (Adam *et al.*, 2017) [2]. Several cellular processes, including DNA replication and protein synthesis, are affected by ochratoxin A (OTA) and deoxynivalenol (DON). Moreover, aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) has been recognized for its carcinogenicity, mostly through genotoxic effects, by the World Health Organization's (WHO) International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) Monographs Program (De Ruyck *et al.*, 2015) [3].

Aflatoxins B1, B2, G1, G2 Among the naturally occurring aflatoxins, the toxic properties of aflatoxin B1 are the most widely studied. Aflatoxins have acute toxic effects (hepatotoxic in humans and animals and immunosuppressive in animals). The major concern, however, is that the aflatoxins are among the most potent mutagenic and carcinogenic substances known. The aflatoxins appeared to be extremely potent carcinogens in animal experiments. They are potent in all species investigated, i.e. mice, rats, hamsters, fish, duck, tree shrews and monkeys, and in several organs, of which the liver is the primary target (CEC, 1996).

Mycotoxins are unavoidable contaminants of spices, posing as health threat to animals and humans. Various studies were conducted to screen various spices for fungi and mycotoxin contamination and evaluate their safety. Aiko and Mehta (2016) [14] studies 63 samples for fungal

contamination and fungal load determined using standard microbiological method. Aflatoxin and citrinin were detected using thin layer chromatography

Chromatography technique. Fifty-eight out of the 63 samples were contaminated, while five were free from fungal contamination. Analysis revealed that 47% of the samples had a fungal load above 1.9×10^3 cfu/g which is the permissible limit set by World Health Organization. The samples *Mesua ferrea*-II and *Terminalia chebula*-III had the highest fungal load, i.e., 5.09×10^4 cfu/g. A total of 187 fungi were isolated, out of which 28 were toxigenic which included 19 aflatoxin-producing *Aspergillus flavus* and 9 citrinin-producing *Penicillium citrinum*. The natural contamination with aflatoxin B1 was detected only in one sample, i.e., *Arachis hypogaea* (groundnut) which was present beyond the permissible limit. Though toxigenic fungi were isolated, mycotoxins were not detected from any of the medicinal herbs and spices. Medicinal herbs and spices are susceptible to toxigenic fungi; however, they also possess intrinsic factors that inhibit mycotoxin contamination.

Quantitative estimation of aflatoxins by HPLC (FSSAI, 2016)

The samples found positive upon thin layer chromatography were further quantified using the High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) using ultraviolet detection at 365 nm. The method used a Shimadzu LC-20AD pump with DGU-20A5 degasser, an automated sample injector system SIL 20A communication module-20A, and UV detector SPD-20A. The HPLC was set at 365 nm with a reverse-phase ODS C18 column (Shim-pack MAqC-ODS; 4.6 x 250

mm, 5 μ m) under a 20 °C controlled column chamber. The samples were kept at 4 °C before injecting

Molecular identification of key species

Based on the present study, the key fungal species, identified either as toxigenic or as antagonistic were further sent for the identification using molecular techniques. The pure cultures of the fungal isolates were sent to the National Centre for Microbial Resource (NCMR), National Centre for Cell Science (NCCS), Pune, India. Briefly, the fungal sample(s) were identified based on Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS). The ITS region is the most widely sequenced DNA region in molecular ecology of fungi and has been recommended as the universal fungal barcode sequence. It has typically been most useful for molecular systematics at the species to genus level, and even within species (e.g., to identify geographic races). The ITS code was matched with National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) database. The confidence in identification came with the availability of sequence and the extent of homology shown by the ~550 bp sequence of fungal sample with its closest neighbour in the database. Shown by the ~550 bp sequence of fungal sample with its closest neighbour in the database.

Results

During the study, various spice samples were collected for the fungal colonization. Various spice samples were procured from the local market of Jabalpur (MP) and the sources included various supermarkets, Grocery stores, as well as spice packing units and warehouses. The samples contained both branded and unbranded products, but the priority was given to the local packers of these spices.

Table 1: Frequency of fungal infestation on different spices collected during the study.

S. No.	Spice	Infestation	Rainy		Winter		Summer		Total	Frequency %
			L	P	L	P	L	P		
1	Coriander	Infested	5	3	4	1	2	3	18	94.74
		Total	5	3	4	2	2	3	19	
2	Red Chilli	Infested	1	3	2	1	3	3	13	86.67
		Total	3	3	2	1	3	3	15	
3	Turmeric	Infested	2	0	3	1	5	0	11	91.67
		Total	3	0	3	1	5	0	12	
4	Cinnamon	Infested	2	2	2	0	1	3	10	100.00
		Total	2	2	2	0	1	3	10	
5	Fenugreek	Infested	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	66.67
		Total	1	0	1	1	0	0	3	
6	Black Pepper	Infested	1	0	0	1	1	1	4	100.00
		Total	1	0	0	1	1	1	4	
7	Cumin	Infested	0	0	0	3	1	1	5	100.00
		Total	0	0	0	3	1	1	5	
8	Bay Leaves	Infested	2	1	1	1	0	2	7	100.00
		Total	2	1	1	1	0	2	7	
9	Clove	Infested	1	1	3	0	4	0	9	90.00
		Total	1	2	3	0	4	0	10	
10	Black Cumin	Infested	2	1	1	0	0	0	4	100.00
		Total	2	1	1	0	0	0	4	
11	Curry Powder	Infested	2	2	2	1	3	1	11	100.00
		Total	2	2	2	1	3	1	11	

Quantification of aflatoxins in spice samples using High Performance Liquid Chromatography

Positive TLC samples were subjected to High Performance Liquid Chromatography to quantify the aflatoxins using HPLC. The quantification was done using the peak area of standard aflatoxins run under the same chromatographic conditions. shows the HPLC chromatogram of four standard aflatoxins. AFG2 was detected at retention time of 10.02 min, followed by AFG1(11.23 min), AFB2 (15.87 min) and AFB1 (16.21 min). The concentration of standard AFG2 and AFB2 were 10 µg while AFG1 and AFB1 were 25 µg.

Table 2: Diameter of *Aspergillus flavus* mycelium growth (in mm) when co- cultured with other non-toxicogenic fungi in a dual culture experiment. Control has the target fungi alone.

S. No	Fungi co-cultured with <i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Radial growth of <i>A. flavus</i> (in mm)						
		Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7
1	Control (<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>)	6	9	11	20	33	52	80
2	<i>Mucor racemosus</i>	6	12	24	28	26	25	25
3	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	6	10	14	18	21	24	24
4	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	6	10	14	15	18	22	22
5	<i>Rhizopus sp.</i>	6	18	31	32	26	25	25
6	<i>Alternaria sp.</i>	6	11	15	19	22	26	26
7	<i>Cladosporium sp.</i>	6	9	11	14	21	24	24
8	<i>Curvularia sp.</i>	6	10	13	17	21	24	24

The results were provided by NCCS using BLAST method based on the nucleotide sequence and NCBI database to the extent of homology by ~550 bp sequence. The nucleotide sequence and identification of fungal strains is given below.

Fig 1: Antagonistic activity of *A. flavus* against *Mucor racemosus*.

Fig 2: Antagonistic activity of *A. flavus* against *Aspergillus niger*

Penicillium polonicum

TCACCTCCACCCGTTTATTTTACCTTGTTGCTTCG
 GCGGGCCCGCCTTTACTGGCCGCCGGGGGCTCAC
 GCCCCGGGCCCGCGCCCGCGAAGACACCCCGA
 ACTCTGTCTGAAGATTGAAGTCTGAGTGAAATAT
 AAATTATTTAAAACCTTTCAACAACGGATCTCTTGGT
 TCCGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATA
 CGTAATGTGAATTGCAAATTCAGTGAATCATCGAG
 TCTTTGAACGCACATTGCGCCCCCTGGTATTCCGGG
 GGGCATGCCTGTCCGAGCGTCATTGCTGCCCTCAA
 GCCCCGCTTGTGTGTTGGGCCCGTCTCCGATTCC
 GGGGGACGGGCCCGAAAGGCAGCGGCGGCACCGC
 GTCCGGTCTCGAGCGTATGGGGCTTTGTCACCCG
 CTCTGTAGGCCCGGCCGGCGCTTGCCGATCAACCC
 AAATTTTTATCCAGGTTGACCTCGGATCAGTAGGG
 ATACCCGCTGAACTTAAGCA.

Penicillium cuddlyae

GGGGTCGGCTGGCGCCGGCCGGGCCTGCAAAGCG
 GGTGACAAAGCCCCATACGCTCGAGGACCGGACGC
 GGTGCCCGCGCTGCCTTTTCGGGCCCGTCCCCGGGG
 GGACGGCGCCCAACACACAAGCCGGGCTTGAGGG
 CAGCAATGACGCTCGGACAGGCATGCCCCCGGAA
 TACCAGGGGGCGCAATGTGCGTTCAAAGACTCGAT
 GATTCACCTGAATTCTGCAATTCACATTACTTCGC
 ATTTTCGCTGCGTTCTTCATCGATGCCGGAACCAAG
 AGATCCGTTGTTGAAAGTTTTAACTAATTTGTGCTT
 ATCGCTCAGACTGCAATCTTCAGACAGCGTTCAAT
 GATGTCTCCGGCGGGCGCGGGCCCGGGGCGAGGTG
 CCCCCGGCGGCCAGACTGGCGGGCCCGCCGAAGC
 AACAAGGTACGGTATACAC.

Fusarium chlamydsporum

TGTGACATACCTATACGTTGCTCGGCGGATCAGC
 CCGCGCCCCGTAAACGGGACGGCCCGCCGAGG
 ACCACAAACCCTGAATTTTATTGTAACCTTCTGAGT
 TTAACAAAACAATAAATCAAAACTTTCAACAACGG
 ATCTCTGGTTCTGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGCA
 AAATGCGATAAGTAATGTGAATTGCAGAATTGAGT
 GAATCATCGAATCTTTGAACGCACATTGCGCCCGC
 CAGTATTCTGGCGGGCATGCCTGTTGAGCGTCATT
 TCAACCCTCAAGCCCCGGGTTTGGTGTGGGGAT
 CGGGCTGCGGTTCTACCGCGTCCCGGCCCGAAAT
 CTAGTGGCGGTCTCGCTGCAGCCTCCATTGCGTAGT
 AGCTAACACCTCGCAACTGGAACGCGCGCGGCC.

It was an important observation that needs to be mentioned that the nucleotide sequence has similar percent of homology with more than one strain of fungi, and hence it is difficult to identify these fungi. We have adopted the molecular taxonomy in conjunction of our earlier recording of macro- and micro-morphological characters.

Discussion

Food is one of the fundamental needs of life. The rapid growth in population raised the food intake requirement. The extremely safe handling, storage and processing conditions are required as the number of commodities increased day today. Microorganisms are present everywhere in our environment. Depending upon the state of occurrence, the microorganisms can either be poisonous or non-poisonous.

Fungi are ubiquitous in nature and can affect plants, animals as well as humans. Fungal contamination of food is not a new phenomenon, and methods to avoid fungal contamination of food are in practice since evolution of mankind (Nazir *et al.*, 2019) ^[12]. Fungal toxins (mycotoxins) are one of the major threats of consuming fungi infested food items by humans and the animals, as these mycotoxins present a wide degree of acute and chronic toxicosis (Thanushree *et al.*, 2019) ^[13].

Conclusion

Although there are more than 300 mycotoxins discovered so far, only few are known to infest food commodities. Spices are reported to have only aflatoxin contaminations, and hence FSSAI has set up the limit of 30 ppm for spices (www.fssai.gov.in). Although this limit is almost twice as the limit of European Union, it is important to note that most of the spices are cultivated in tropical conditions, including India, where knowledge about toxin contamination and technological advantage for storage and transport is negligible.

References

1. Kumar S, Kumar. Ultra wide field imaging of coats like response in Leber's congenital amaurosis. *Saudi J Ophthalmol.* 2017;31:122-123.
2. Adam KC, Vogel EK, Awh E. Clear evidence for item limits in visual working memory. *Cognitive psychology.* 2017;97:79-97.
3. Ruyck De K, De Boevre M, Huybrechts I, De Saeger S. Dietary mycotoxins, co-exposure, and carcinogenesis in humans: Short review. *Mutation Research/Reviews in*

4. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Outbreak of aflatoxin poisoning—eastern and central provinces, Kenya, January–July 2004. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2004;53(34):790.
5. Chambergo FS, Valencia EY. Fungal biodiversity to biotechnology. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2016;100(6):2567-2577.
6. Chang PK. The *Aspergillus parasiticus* protein AFLJ interacts with the aflatoxin pathway-specific regulator AFLR. *Mol Genet Genomics.* 2003;268(6):711-719.
7. Chang PK, Horn BW, Dorner JW. Clustered genes involved in cyclopiazonic acid production are next to the aflatoxin biosynthesis gene cluster in *Aspergillus flavus*. *Fungal Genet Biol.* 2009;46(2):176-182.
8. Chang PK, Yu J, Yu JH. aflT, a MFS transporter-encoding gene located in the aflatoxin gene cluster, does not have a significant role in aflatoxin secretion. *Fungal Genet Biol.* 2004;41(10):911-920.
9. MAFRI-Manitoba Agriculture, Food and Rural Initiatives. Grain drying and storage of damp grain—crop production. 2006.
10. Magnoli C, Astoreca A, Ponsone LG, Fernández-Juri MG, Chiacchiera S, Dalcerro A. Ochratoxin A and the occurrence of ochratoxin A-producing black aspergilli in stored peanut seeds from Córdoba, Argentina. *J Sci Food Agric.* 2006;86(14):2369-2373.
11. Makhlof J, Carvajal-Campos A, Querin A, Tadrist S, Puel O, *et al.* Morphologic, molecular and metabolic characterization of *Aspergillus* section Flavi in spices marketed in Lebanon. *Sci Rep.* 2019;9(1):1-11.
12. Nazir S, Ali Y, Ullah N, García-Magariño I. Internet of things for healthcare using effects of mobile computing: a systematic literature review. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing.* 2019;2019(1):5931315.
13. Thanushree MP, Sailendri D, Yoha KS, Moses JA, Anandharamakrishnan C. Mycotoxin contamination in food: An exposition on spices. *Trends in Food Science & Technology.* 2019;93:69-80.
14. Aiko V, Edamana P, Mehta A. Decomposition and detoxification of aflatoxin B1 by lactic acid. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture.* 2016;96(6):1959-1966.

Creative Commons (CC) License

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license. This license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.